

PRIME PETE HANDBOOK AND GUIDANCE MATERIAL

Discover and implement new education content for
primary Physical Education teachers

PRIME PETE
PRIMARY EDUCATION PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION

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For further information on the PRIME PETE Project please follow the link:

Website: <http://www.primepete.com>

Project partners

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Figure 1 Overview of the project partners in Europe

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Introduction

This handbook and guidance material is designed to support the easy and flexible implementation of the modular PRIME PETE programme. In the project process, this document represents Intellectual Output #8.

The target groups addressed by the handbook and guidance material are the following:

- Teacher education institutions;
- Teacher educators;
- Researchers active in the field of teacher education;
- Primary teachers teaching primary PE;
- NGO's like research associations, teacher associations, etc.;
- Stakeholders and policy makers with responsibility for teacher education.

The handbook and guidance material first provides a summary about the project in general (pp. 6-8) and the Intellectual Outputs #1-8 and IO#10 realized in the PRIME PETE project (pp. 9-38) to provide the reader with background knowledge on how the programme came to be. Following this, users will find guidance material in the form of screenshots and descriptions on navigating the website (IO#9) (pp. 39-40) and the self-check tool and feedback report (pp. 43-48). This is followed with concluding remarks. This document is available online in its final version as an open access resource.

With the help of this handbook, an easy and flexible implementation of the modular Physical Education Teacher Education (PETE) programme in different contexts is possible, which helps to pursue the mission of the PRIME PETE project:

The PRIME PETE Mission

The mission of PRIME PETE is to prepare student teachers (generalists or specialists) as competent, analytically reflective, professionally effective professionals who are cognisant of personal health and wellbeing as they teach primary physical education.

The PRIME PETE project

The Primary Physical Education Teacher Education (PRIME PETE) project is an Erasmus+ project that aims to develop a general approach to PETE that allows adaptation to national/regional contexts and/or different phases of teacher education.

The objectives of the project were the following:

Objectives of the project

- to bring together European HEI and other stakeholders active in Primary PETE and to foster their cooperation in PETE and mobility exchange
- to provide an overview of Primary PETE in Europe
- to inform and facilitate the formulation of a profile of a primary PE teacher and a modular curriculum for Primary PETE based on this profile and core principles
- to make this modular curriculum available for any interested stakeholders
- to foster the delivery of quality physical education (QPE) in primary education by strengthening the primary PE teacher profession

These objectives were achieved by developing step-by-step the intellectual outputs of the project which are reflected in the figure below (Fig. 2):

Figure 2 Steps of the PRIME PETE project

Each of the ten intellectual outputs created a basis for the development of the modular primary physical education programme which is the core of the PRIME PETE project.

These ten project outputs can help the institutions as well as the individuals to develop tailored primary PETE programme that will contribute to higher quality PE teacher education. The project partners understand the difficulty in accreditation processes and development phases of teacher education programmes in different contexts, however the outputs of the PRIME PETE project can help to re-design and re-think the current approaches at Higher Education Institutions (HEI) with the purpose to prepare primary PE teachers to deliver quality physical education in schools.

All the outputs together with descriptions are summarized and available to read and download on the project website www.primepete.com and are summarised in the following sections.

Figure 3 The PRIME PETE Website

OVERVIEW ON PRIMARY PETE IN EUROPE

Aim of the intellectual output

Mapping of the current situation in Primary PETE in Europe

- Existing profiles for primary teachers teaching PE in Europe
- Existing concepts, models and curricula for Primary PETE in Europe
- Existing links to European frameworks, as e.g. the European Qualification Framework (EQF)

3 ways to extract information:

Landscape Analysis

Literature Review

Delphi Study

LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

The project partners analyzed information on PETE in 25 countries through available literature informed also by their own knowledge and by institutional documents describing the current situations in the different countries.

Information is organised using the following categories and sub categories (MacPhail et al., 2019) to provide an overview on PETE in Europe:

- Teachers' Qualification Level
- Initial Teacher Education
- Induction Phase
- In-service Provision

Teachers' Qualification Level

Similarities as well as differences in providing primary PETE in Europe

- The Bologna process enabled larger coherence of the study programmes at the Higher Education Institutions
- However, number of ECTS, content or provision of school placement vary considerably among the European countries

Figure 4 Number of ECTS for PE modules in different European Countries

The number of credits starts with 5 ECTS for PE modules and increases to 75 ECTS (German North-Rhine Westphalia). The number of ECTS does not include the school placement and the bachelor or master thesis.

The average amount of credits offered to PE modules in case of generalist teachers is 8 ECTS. In case of specialist teachers, the average number of credits is 36 ECTS.

Initial Teacher Education

Countries have different **admission processes** to their study programmes at their institutions. The most common criteria for admission are from secondary school examination results. Some of the universities include motor aptitudes fitness tests in their admission process (Hungary, Sweden). Luxembourg requires admissions in languages (Luxembourgish, German, English and French), but also in math and natural science. In Ireland competency in the Irish language is required. The form of the admissions is either as written test or an interview.

School placement is considered a crucial element for achieving quality teaching. In the sample of European countries that were analysed within the project, the school placement was organised in various ways. In most of the cases, there were no specific recommendations or rules for school placement related to PE.

Induction Phase

Induction phase starts with zero years in some countries and the longest period of induction in the countries' sample is 2 years.

Figure 5 The length of the induction in years in different European Countries

In-service Provision

In-service teacher education is in most of the participating countries optional (74%), providers differ between countries (most Higher Education Institutions).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reading of the published literature and available documents to extract relevant information to develop a PRIME PETE framework.

- Identify and highlight findings from the published literature that can inform the development of the PRIME PETE framework
- Analysing available documents, and extracting relevant information for the framework
 - explicit recommendations ('teacher trainers should ...')
 - implicit ideas (e.g., 'teacher education seems to be effective when it ...')
 - empirical

Findings of the literature review were grouped in six dimensions, based on the content of the CALOHEE teacher education framework (González & Yarosh, 2018).

Table 1 Findings of the literature review

Knowledge, Management and Creation	→ school experiences → reflective approaches → lifelong learning → ...
Design and Management of Process of Learning, Teaching and Assessment	→ digitalisation, inclusion and experiential education → routines → curricula enhancement → ...
Learner Empowerment, Potential and Creativity supporting Learner Holistic Growth and Development	→ development of a teacher's knowledge is an iterative process → support a healthy work-related behavioural → professional biography support → ...

<p>Values and Social Leadership: Ethics and Social Commitment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → collaborative work between teachers → combining didactics with practical parts → incorporation of inclusive physical education → ...
<p>Communication with Different Actors and in Different Contexts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → verbal and non-verbal communication routines → professional exchanges, and lesson observation → social media and communication technologies → ...
<p>Development as Professionals and Life-Long Learners</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → professional development as an essential component of professional life → informal physical education leadership with a shared approach → occasion of pre-services to exchange and reflect alongside with experienced teachers → ...

The PRIME PETE Delphi consensus study aimed to adapt and reword each of the CALOHEE dimensions and statements to a PETE-specific content.

Table 2 Adaptation of the CALOHEE Dimensions

ORIGINAL CALOHEE DIMENSIONS	PRIME PETE DIMENSIONS
DIMENSION 1. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND CREATION	DIMENSION 1. KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT
DIMENSION 2. DESIGN AND MANAGEMENT OF PROCESSES OF LEARNING, TEACHING AND ASSESSMENT	DIMENSION 2. TEACHING, LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT
DIMENSION 3. LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL AND CREATIVITY: Supporting learner holistic growth and development	DIMENSION 3. LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL, DIVERSITY AND CREATIVITY
DIMENSION 4. VALUES AND SOCIAL LEADERSHIP: Ethics and social commitment	DIMENSION 4. VALUES, SOCIAL LEADERSHIP AND COMMUNICATION
DIMENSION 5. COMMUNICATION: Communication with different actors and in different contexts	
DIMENSION 6. DEVELOPMENT AS PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS	DIMENSION 5. DEVELOPMENT AS REFLECTIVE PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS

DELPHI STUDY

Participants: 38 groups with 220 PE experts from 36 countries performed a Delphi Consensus Study on the six dimensions of the CALOHEE teacher education framework, adapted previously for Primary PETE.

Figure 6 Process of the Delphi Study

Five dimensions with associated statements revealed by the Delphi study:

D1: Knowledge Development and Management

- Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills
- Knowledge about children's overall development
- Knowledge of PA recommendations for children and young people

D2: Teaching, Learning and Assessment

- Ability to plan and teach QPE lessons
- Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment in PE
- Ability to plan long and short-term PE programmes based on students' developmental level and readiness

D3: Learner Empowerment, Potential, Diversity and Creativity

- Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels
- Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment
- Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence

D4: Values, Social Leadership and Communication

- Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students
- Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and non-verbally
- Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting in PE

D5: Development as Reflective Professionals and Life-long Learners

- Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for PE in the school and beyond

If you would like to read more about the IO#1, please click the button below to download the full report (Masarykova et al., 2023).

[Please click here for the full report of this intellectual output](#)

RECOMMENDATIONS ON PRIMARY PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION

The recommendations made below result from an integration work of the recommendations arising from 3 sources of the project:

- the output of the Literature Review on Prime PETE;
- the output of the Delphi study;
- and the Learning Teaching and Training¹ meeting 1 output.

The recommendations are allocated to the dimensions formulated through the Delphi study. The following is an example of a recommendation for each dimension. The complete recommendations can be found on the PRME PETE website under [this link](#).

- Minimum compulsory ECTS for specific PE subjects (by increasing the existing or including modules or teaching units), for both generalist and specialist teacher education.
- Education courses for specialist and generalist primary school teachers must have subjects or modules that allow analysis of children's overall development and, advanced knowledge and understanding of motor development and learning of children between 5 and 10 years and its implications for the teaching-learning of PE.
- Education courses for specialists and generalist primary school teachers must have subjects or modules that can facilitate the integration of PE in the multidisciplinary educational process of primary education (for instance by using multidisciplinary work groups).
- Education courses for specialists and generalist primary school teachers must have subjects or modules oriented towards knowledge of the PE curriculum in primary school and its impact on later learning experiences in school and throughout their life
- Knowledge that allows implementation of the official curriculum of primary education in PE.

¹ Learning Teaching and Training (LTT) 1 : Higher Education Institutions project partner presentations

- Subjects or Modules oriented to improve the teaching-learning competence with a focus on the pedagogical content knowledge (how students are learning the PE contents, with the key focus on enhancing PE teaching in primary schools).
- High rate of compulsory practical classes or practical experiences in contexts that allow contact with the specificity of PE teaching.
- Training courses for generalist teachers providing adequate time to explore PE teaching methods and promote a holistic vision of this subject that affects physical, social, personal, cognitive and emotional development.
- Important considerations that need to be highlighted by PE teacher educators include individualization, diversity, and special needs.
- Regular professional exchanges and lesson observation are desirable as well as the use of social media and communication technologies that may be beneficial for exchange between teachers acting as reflective practitioners.

If you would like to read more about the IO#2, please click the button below to download the full report (Onofre et al., 2023).

[Please click here for the full report of this intellectual output](#)

PRIMARY PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER PROFILE

Aim of the intellectual output

- to develop the primary PE teacher profile (core and extended competences requirement – for teachers teaching PE)
- to identify conclusions to inform the development of a theoretical and methodological framework for primary Physical Education Teacher Education (IO#4).

Two key elements informed the development of the framework for the Primary Physical Education Teacher Profile (PPETP):

- CALOHEE teacher education framework (González & Yarosh, 2018)
- the PRIME PETE Delphi study.

The profile is based on the dimensions developed in the Delphi study (see description of the Delphi Study on page 16). Each one of these wide dimensions is better **defined by a subset of core (upper part) and extended (lower part) knowledge, skills, and competencies elements.**

The PRIME PETE projects has developed a profile for generalist PE teachers and specialist PE teachers. The dimensions outlined within the profile are designed to provide guidance for both generalists and specialists across dimensions that are identified as 'core dimensions' and further dimensions described as 'extended dimensions'. As the Specialist benefits from more time for PE specific education, the profile may be wider or deeper. The following tables are containing all the requirements in each dimension (1-5). The white colour presents the core knowledge, skills, and competencies, the red colour presents the extended knowledge, skills, and competencies. The individual statements grouped by the descriptors *Knowledge, Skills* and *Autonomy and Responsibility (Wider Competences)*. Codes were then applied to each statement (e.g. D1K1 means Dimension 1 - Knowledge statement 1). These codes can also be found in the description of the individual modules and micro-modules.

Table 3 Dimensions of the PE Teacher Profile

Dimension 1: KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT			
	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
Core Dimensions	D1K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills	D1S1 Ability to use basic educational research, and applying existing theories and educational methods, to enhance teaching	D1C1 Capacity and autonomy to modify and adapt core educational and curricular policies to pedagogical practice
	D1K2 Knowledge about children’s overall development	D1S2 Ability to arrange pedagogical work in line with policies of an education system and educational theories	
	D1K3 Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people	D1S3 Ability to use evidence-based educational theories and practices and ignore pseudoscientific claims and programmes	
	D1K4 Knowledge and understanding of the cultures of physical activity, physical education, and sport		
Extended Dimensions	D1K5 Advanced knowledge and understanding of holistic and learner-focused educational approaches to physical education and health education		D1C2 Capacity and responsibility to integrate key competency development to the physical education programme
	D1K6 Advanced knowledge and understanding of the role and significance of the body as a means of creative expression and artistic communication through exploration of a wide range of content within physical education		D1C3 Capacity and commitment to using physical education specific concepts and terminology appropriately
	D1K7 Advanced knowledge and critical understanding of sociological, philosophical, psychological and pedagogical theories in education and physical education		D1C4 Capacity and commitment to critically reflect on educational policies

the codes used here can also be found in the description of the individual modules and micro-modules. delete this from here add text above

Dimension 2: TEACHING, LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT

	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
Core Dimensions	D2K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding for cross-thematic and interdisciplinary teaching in physical education	D2S1 Ability to plan and teach quality physical education lessons	
		D2S2 Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment	
		D2S3 Ability to plan long-term and short-term physical education programmes based on students' developmental level and readiness	
		D2S4 Ability to demonstrate correctly, or provide a correct demonstration through a third party, of all major skills and tactics central to the relevant curriculum	
		D2S5 Ability to using digital technology for learning and assessment	
Extended Dimensions	D2K2 Advanced knowledge of group dynamics (including conflict management) and student-centered strategies	D2S6 Ability to promote efficient use of movement time	D2C1 Capacity and commitment to cooperate with other teachers and develop school curricula based on reflection
	D2K3 Advanced knowledge of the national curriculum	D2S7 Ability to use observation, self- and peer-assessment in physical education lessons and programmes	D2C2 Capacity and commitment to using different teaching strategies and model-based teaching in physical education lessons
	D2K4 Advanced knowledge and understanding of different motor learning theories, and typical and atypical motor development, and practical consequences	D2S8 Ability to use teaching skills to support learning in different learning environments	D2C3 Analyse and critique playgrounds, outdoor areas and parks as places for learning in physical education
	D2K5 Advanced knowledge on how to measure, reflect and evaluate physical education programmes		

Dimension 3: LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL, DIVERSITY AND CREATIVITY

	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
Core Dimensions	D3K1 Advanced knowledge of inclusion principles and practices	D3S1 Ability to support learners in identifying own strengths and setting goals to build on these	D3C1 Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels
		D3S2 Ability to work together with special education professionals, and adapt learning tasks to the individual needs of the students	D3C2 Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment
			D3C3 Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence
Extended Dimensions	D3K2 Advanced knowledge and commitment to the application of the concept of the student as an active learner, thinker, mover and problem solver engaging with the content of the physical education curriculum	D3S3 Ability to build upon students' previous experiences, active participation, and creativity	
	D3K3 Advanced knowledge and understanding to recognise and differentiate healthy competitive and non-competitive concepts	D3S4 Ability to design autonomy supported learning environment, and mastery learning	
	D3K4 Advanced knowledge of school counseling processes and of how to advise students (and their families/guardians) to develop learners' resources	D3S5 Ability to motivate students to practice sport activities in collaboration with peers, families and sport coaches	
		D3S6 Ability to support students learning through an examination of a range of resources and equipment related to teaching physical education	

Dimension 4: VALUES, SOCIAL LEADERSHIP AND COMMUNICATION

	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
Core Dimensions	D2K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding for cross-thematic and interdisciplinary teaching in physical education	D4S1 Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and nonverbally	D4C1 Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students
		D4S2 Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting	D4C2 Capacity and commitment to respect different values, when interacting with people in contexts of diversity (social, ethnic, economic, political) and learn from that diversity
		D4S3 Ability to reflect on personal capacity, qualities and competencies as a subject leader in physical education	D4C3 Capacity and commitment to adhere to children's rights
Extended Dimensions	D2K2 Advanced knowledge of group dynamics (including conflict management) and student-centered strategies	D4S4 Ability to create situations for recognising and understanding fair-play	D4C4 Capacity and commitment to take responsibility to promote and/or initiate teamwork among learners
		D4S5 Ability to organise extracurricular activities, and other educational events in response to social need	D4C5 Capacity and commitment to work with external providers to support learning in physical education
			D4C6 Capacity and commitment to promoting responsible and critical use of social media and communication technologies among learners

Dimension 5: DEVELOPMENT AS REFLECTIVE PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS			
	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS	AUTONOMY AND RESPONSIBILITY (WIDER COMPETENCES)
Core Dimensions			D5C1 Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for physical education in the school and beyond
			D5C2 Capacity and commitment to make use of colleagues, professional organisations and resources to develop as a reflective practitioner
			D5C3 Capacity and commitment to “cultural literacy” to support students coming from other cultures
Extended Dimensions	D5K1 Advanced knowledge of main sources of information that permit teachers to stay updated with general and physical education-related educational research and developments	D5S1 Ability to critically examine educational research and developments (publications, events, resources, etc.) in search of solutions for challenges experienced in own classroom	D5C4 Capacity and commitment to critically reflect and work on consistency of own personal and professional identity
		D5S2 Ability to develop adequate coping strategies, social support or preventive identification and influencing of stressors in the private and professional context	D5C5 Capacity and commitment to identify opportunities for collaboration and professional dialogue where teachers can develop networks, undertake peer observations and engage in collaborative professional learning
		D5S3 Ability to promote health and wellbeing concept by supporting active reflection about their job	D5C6 Capacity and commitment to ongoing professional development through the design of a professional development plan to guide growth as a physical education teacher

By outlining the key elements in the profile (PPETP), it can **serve as a checklist for existing teacher education programmes, and a guideline** for those still being developed (see chapter [The self-check tool and feedback report](#) on page 43).

This checklist constitutes a way to compare the dimensions of the profile suggested in the project PRIME PETE and the **reality of the profile of the user’s institution**.

If you would like to read more about the IO#3, please click the button below to download the full report (Repond et al., 2023).

[Please click here for the full report of this intellectual output](#)

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR PRIMARY PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION IN EUROPE

Aim of the intellectual output

- Provide theoretical and methodological guidelines for a modular study programme for Primary PETE based on the previous findings and recommendations from PRIME PETE IO#1-3.

In order to address the prospective teachers on the one hand and the desirable study programmes on the other hand, it is necessary to consider what constitutes these in terms of quality.

Successful Graduates need to

- Display specific competences
- Present reasoned rational argument for the long-term benefits of PE.
- Adopt evolutionary, critical approaches to the place of PE in the educational process.

Study Programmes need to feature

- A well-adjusted combination of theoretical, practical and professional work
- Practical activities, educational and teaching sciences, natural and biological sciences, social sciences/humanities, scientific work and school-based teaching practice
- Universal Design for Learning (UDL) as a methodological framework for the design of courses.
- Elements (modules) that can be organized into themes to provide a structure for programmes.

Figure 6 presents a structure for primary PETE programme design which will guide us through the process of providing its specific elements.

Figure 7 Primary PETE Programme Model

PRIME PETE Mission

The mission of the Prime Pete programme is to prepare student teachers at undergraduate level for a successful future as PE educators who build communities of competent and knowledgeable children on their physical literacy journey who value an active and healthy lifestyle and pursue physical activity. The primary PE teacher (generalist or specialist) is seen as a competent professional who is concerned to become more effective in assisting and enabling children's physical, social and cognitive learning and development within a variety of contexts through analysing, exploring and reflecting upon their practice.

Table 4 Broad aspects of the Prime Pete Programme for Generalist and Specialist Physical Education Teachers

PRIMARY PETE MISSION		THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK	COMPETENCES		ELEMENTS (Modules)	Meth. progr. design	CORE THEMES		
	SOURCE			SOURCE		SOURCE		SOURCE	
Competent	LR, LTT	Behaviourism	Life-long learner	R#8, IO#2, LR	Practical Activities (Theory and Practice), Educational and Teaching Sciences (Pedagogy and Didactics), Natural and Biological Sciences (General and Applied), Social Sciences/Humanities (General and Applied), Scientific Work (Research Project, Master or Bachelor Final Essay), School-based Teaching Practice (School placement / general and specific)	LTT, LR	UDL	a. QPE	D2, D4, LR
Analytically reflective	LR	Constructivism	Command of PE knowledge	D1, LTT, LR		LTT		b. Practical activities / competent movers / physical literacy	D1, LR
Professionally effective	D5, LTT, LR	Communities of Practice	Organised	D2, D3, D4, LR		LR		c. Professional identity, professional relationships	D5
Cognisant of one's health and well-being	LR	Connectivism	Reflective	LR		LR		d. Child development, safety	D1, D2, LR D5, LTT
			Analytical	LR, LTT		LR		e. Wellbeing of child and student teacher	D4
			Ethical	D4		LR, LTT		f. Subject knowledge, inclusion, assessment	D1, D2, D3, D4, LTT, LR
			Caring	D3				g. Teaching strategies, development of digital skills	D5, LTT
			Empathetic	D3, D4				h. Research [physical education topic]	LTT, LR
			Respectful	R#8					
			Inclusive	D2, D3, D4, LR					
			Good communicator	D3, D5					
			Collaborative	R#7, R#8					
			Researcher	R#9					
			Competent	R#2					

Note: IO#2 Report: LR=Literature Review; LTT= Learning Teaching and Training, #IO1 and #IO3: D1, D2, D3, D4, D5 = Dimensions Round 3 only Delphi Study; R#2, #7, #8, #9 = Recommendations from IO#2

UDL = Universal Design for Learning

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Various *Learning Theories* are suggested with two particular key messages emanating from these:

- In a single day, a student may engage with behaviorism-inspired videos with mastery quizzes, connect on social media to a community of practice for advice on solving a homework question, use responses to help their construction of understanding of a topic, and post a social media comment where they share their understanding and the resources that helped them.
- Efficient PETE programmes balance field-based learning experiences with on-campus opportunities for continued learning and reflection through constructivist-oriented learning strategies that promote reflection and critical thinking.

Core themes

The organisation of the elements of study programmes into themes provides a means of highlighting key aspects for teaching primary PE. These core themes of Quality Physical Education are represented here:

Elements

Primary PETE programmes of study (240/300 ECTS credits over 4-5 years) could be structured to facilitate students passing through 3 phases – foundation (Year 1), extension (Year 2) and specialization (Years 3 & 4):

- **Year 1** modules provide a comprehensive introduction to the principles underpinning the study and teaching of PE in Primary Schools;
- **Year 2** modules examine in greater depth areas that were raised in Year 1;
- Modules in **Years 3 and 4** require students to consider their evolving experience in the programme in general and PE in particular,
- Finally integrating theory and practice in a personal independent dissertational or research project study

- **Universal Design for Learning (UDL)** was chosen as the central method for the design of the projects' modular programme for the following reasons: Flexibility in how instructional material is presented, how students demonstrate their knowledge and skills, and how they are engaged in learning.
- Uses a diversity of teaching methods to eliminate any barriers to learning.
- The fundamental goal of UDL is for all students to become expert learners. Expert learners are purposeful and motivated, resourceful and well-informed, and strategic and goal-directed about learning.
- UDL's principles: engagement, representation, and action and expression

The PRIME PETE study programme is the core of the PRIME PETE project and is presented in the next section (Intellectual Output #5).

PRIME PETE = Modular study programme

Modular approach divides the study programme into **independent, non-consecutive, short and small modules or units**.

If you would like to read more about the IO#4, please click the button below to download the full report (Ries et al., 2023).

[Please click here for the full report of this intellectual output](#)

MODULAR PRIMARY PETE PROGRAMME CONSISTING OF COURSE MODULES AND MICRO-MODULES

Aim of the intellectual output

The development of the modular primary PRIME PETE programme consisting of course modules (M) and micro-modules (MM) with exemplars to support the development of primary physical education teacher education programmes in Europe

Modules and Micro Modules were informed by the

- Expertise of project partners
- Outcomes of
 - IO#1 Literature Review & Delphi Study
 - IO#2 Recommendations on Primary PE Teacher Education
 - IO#3 Primary PE Teacher Profile
 - IO#4 The theoretical and methodological framework for primary PETE
 - Learning Teaching and Training Events Brixen, June 2022 and Lisbon, Sept 2022

Module and Micro Module Development

The development of the modular programme is outlined in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8 Module and Micro Module Development process

The PRIME PETE suite of module (M) and micro module (MM) exemplars is now on the PRIME PETE [website](#)

- It is the first **European teacher education programme** for primary physical education available online
- It may be used by **target groups** to support the development of teacher education programmes with a focus on teaching of primary physical education
- It provides **flexibility using a modular** approach
- It can be implemented using **blended or face to face** delivery
- It can **facilitate student and staff mobility** between universities across Europe
- The M and MM can inform **professional development** in undergraduate, post-graduate and in-service settings.

Figure 9 below illustrates an example of the presentation of a module on the website

Planning and Implementation of Physical Education

This module provides first insights into a physical education curriculum for primary school in a country or jurisdiction. The different areas of a curriculum will be presented as main topics of the different courses and students will have to prepare teaching activities in each curriculum area for the subsequent course. This preparation work will be done in groups and the activities will be implemented in the practical part of the course in a gym. A template for lesson preparation will be used to prepare and describe the teaching activities and feedback from peers and the teacher educator will have to be collected during and after the implementation of the activities.

Suggested Number of ECTS

2

Teaching Methodologies

Seminars with lecture part and practical seminar part in the gym

Group work (preparation of lesson examples)

Dimensions Core

D2\$1

D2\$2

D2\$3

Indicative Content

Mobilising basic motor skills

Measure your strengths in a playful way

Participating in Individual and Group Games

MODULE LEARNING OUTCOMES

- LO1: plan movement activities according to the child's age-specific motor development to specifically promote the child's movement behaviour.
- LO2: distinguish between motor skills and abilities.
- LO3: plan, conduct and evaluate physical education lessons considering teaching, instructional and curricular issues.
- LO4: plan and carry out activities within the framework of physical education, considering didactic-methodical principles.

Figure 9 Example of the Modules/Micro-Modules presentation on the website

MODULES AND MICRO MODULES OVERVIEW

Click on the name of the module, micro module or overarching element to go to the content on the website.

Table 5 Modules and Micro Modules Overview

M1	<u>Planning and Implementation of physical education</u>
MM1.1	<u>Planning and Implementation of Physical Education: Child-appropriate Physical Education</u>
M2	<u>Active School Models</u>
MM2.1	<u>Active School Models: Active School</u>
M3	<u>Understanding Physical Education</u>
MM3.1	<u>Understanding Physical Education: Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</u>
MM3.2	<u>Understanding Physical Education: Creative Dance</u>
MM3.3	<u>Understanding Physical Education: Fundamental Movement Skills</u>
M4	<u>Foundations of Primary Physical Education</u>
MM4.1	<u>Foundations of Physical Education: Knowledge and Understanding of Physical Activity Recommendations</u>
MM4.2	<u>Foundations of Primary Physical Education: Motivation, Motivational Climate and Enjoyment in Physical Education</u>
MM4.3	<u>Foundations of Primary Physical Education: Values-based Education through Sport and Physical Education</u>
M5	<u>Didactics of Physical Education</u>
MM5.1	<u>Didactics of Physical Education: Communication and Interaction</u>
MM5.2	<u>Didactics of Physical Education: Organisation and Classroom Management</u>
M6	<u>School Physical and Health Education</u>
MM6.1	<u>School Physical and Health Education: Inclusive Primary Physical Education</u>
MM6.2	<u>School Physical and Health Education: Swimming as a Tool to Support Lifelong Physical Activity</u>
M7	<u>Teaching Physical Education</u>
MM7.1	<u>Teaching Physical Education: Motor Development, Learning and Implications for Teaching</u>
MM7.2	<u>Teaching Physical Education: Classroom Management</u>
M8	<u>Learning to Move in Water in Physical Education</u>
M9	<u>Inclusive Primary Physical Education</u>
M10	<u>Pedagogical Project in Physical Education</u>
M11	<u>Theory and Practice in Physical Education</u>
M12	<u>Development and Implementation of Extracurricular Activities</u>
M13	<u>Subject Leadership in Physical Education</u>
OA1	<u>Professional Placement in Physical Education</u>
OA2	<u>The Teacher as a Reflective Practitioner in Physical Education</u>
OA3	<u>Research in Physical Education</u>

 Modules (M)
 Micro-Modules (MM)
 Overarching Elements (OA)

The modular primary PETE programme consists of course modules and micro-modules based on the theoretical and methodological framework for primary PETE (IO#4). In addition, the programme also contains three overarching elements that can enrich the education of prospective primary school physical education teachers. The programme is available in a dynamic format or as a pdf version for download. The teaching elements are developed in the English language.

Figure 10 Screenshot of the teaching elements page on the website

On the website, a comprehensive table that lists all the modules (M), micro-modules (MM) and Overarching Elements (OA) is provided underneath the tabs for these. The table links these M, MM and OE to the dimensions of the primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP, IO#3) with the help of codes formed to support easy reference.

[Click here to visit the teaching elements page on the PRIME PETE Website](#)

If you would like to read more about the IO#5, please click the button below to download the full report (Marron et al., 2023).

[Please click here for the full report of this intellectual output](#)

METHOD AND TOOL TO EVALUATE THE PETE COURSE MODULES AND MICRO-MODULES

The purpose of this evaluation process was to

- develop a method and tool(s) to evaluate the PRIME PETE course modules and micro-modules
- provide feedback from the Learning Teaching and Training (LTT) 2 event in Brixen to feed forward to the planning, design, and development of the micro-modules at the following LTT 3 in Lisbon
- increase the user's awareness of the results when using the PRIME PETE website and materials
- provide a template for future use for evaluation purposes

The Questionnaires for Students and Educators consists of three parts:

Demographic Information	Evaluation of the LTT 2 and 3 professional development events Brixen and Lisbon	Evaluation of the module and micro-module
Age, Gender, Country of residence, Year if Studies/Teaching Experience	Organizational aspects, teaching and content, implementation and feasibility of the event, recommending the event to peers	Learning, Teaching, Assessment, Feedback, Workload, Skills, Development, Management, Learning environment, overall satisfaction with the module; recommending the module to peers

PRIME PETE Professional Development Event and Module Evaluation tool for Students

Please help enhance the quality of the Professional Development Event and our modules by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Part 1: General Information

- 1.1. Country: _____
- 1.2. University / Faculty: _____
- 1.3. Are you:
 Student Educator
- 1.4. If you are a student, your Study program is:
 Bachelor Master
- 1.5. If you are a student, your Teacher program:
 Specialist PE Generalist Generalist with PE Specialism
- 1.6. If you are a student: Year of studies: _____
- 1.7. Age: _____
- 1.8. Gender: _____
- 1.9. Educator: Years of teaching experience at Third level Initial Teacher Education: _____
- 1.10. Educator: Years of teaching experience at Primary and Secondary level: _____

PRIME PETE Professional Development Event and Module Evaluation tool for Educators

Figure 11 Screenshot on the Student Questionnaire

Please help enhance the quality of the Professional Development Event and our modules by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Part 1: General Information

- 1.1. Country: _____
- 1.2. University / Faculty / Organization: _____
- 1.3. Are you:
 Student Educator
- 1.4. If you are a student, your Study program is:
 Bachelor Master
- 1.5. If you are a student, your Teacher program:
 Specialist PE Generalist Generalist with PE Specialism
- 1.6. If you are a student: Year of studies: _____
- 1.7. Age: _____
- 1.8. _____
- 1.9. Gender: _____
- 1.10. Educator Years of teaching experience at Third level Initial Teacher Education: _____
- 1.11. Educator Years of teaching experience at Primary and Secondary level: _____

If you would like to read more about the IO#5, please click the button below to download the full report (Adamakis et al., 2023).

EVALUATION STUDY AND REPORT

- Evaluation of two Professional Development Events (PDE) (Brixen & Lisbon)
- Evaluation of the micro-modules taught during these PDEs
 - Students
 - Educators
- Evaluation of the micro-modules in partner institutions
 - Students
 - Educators

Facts and figures

24 educators

(16 males,
8 females)

65 students

(11 males,
54 females)

37 PDE forms

25 evaluation forms from the 1st PDE

12 evaluation forms from the 2nd PDE

231
micro-module evaluation forms

107 micro-module evaluation forms
from the 1st PDE

55 micro-module evaluation forms
from the 2nd PDE

69 micro-module evaluation forms
from the partner institutions

Feedbacks about the Professional Development Events

- designed and logically structured, and the overall presentation was adequately employed
- enjoyed participating in these events and they would recommend them to their peers
- positive aspects: practical sessions implemented, the overall positive engagement and interaction between students and educators, the variety of teaching approaches used, and the international perspective of the events
- negative aspect: too packed with activities, not much time available for constructive reflection.
- To improve future similar events, most participants suggested including more practical and micro-teaching sessions and reflections intermediated with the theoretical sessions in the gym.

If you would like to read more about the IO#7, please click the button below to download the full report (Adamakis & Scheuer, 2023).

[Please click here for the full report of this intellectual output](#)

HANDBOOK AND GUIDANCE MATERIAL FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MODULAR PRIMARY PETE PROGRAMME

Similar to the website, this handbook tries to summarise all the important information from the PRIME PETE Project and make it accessible and user-friendly

This handbook and guidance material for the implementation of the modular PETE programme based on the outcomes of IO#1, IO#2, IO#3, IO#4 and especially IO#5 was developed in form of a manual available online. The handbook and guidance material can help to facilitate an easy and flexible implementation of the modular PETE programme in different contexts.

The future users of the PETE programme and its course modules will find here support and guidance when it comes to the implementation in their respective contexts. The guidance material was made available in one well-structured place – this handbook – to facilitate this kind of implementation.

The document is available online in its final version as an open access resource.

Figure 13 Screenshot of the Handbook Cover

OPEN COURSE PLATFORM

At the website <https://www.primepete.com/> you can find all information related to the PRIME PETE project. The following image shows a screenshot of the landing page, which you can use to navigate to different topics. The image shows which information is behind which tab.

Figure 14 Screenshot Landing Page with navigation aid

The intellectual outputs tab contains an overview of the results produced in the project.

Click on the button to get a short summary of each output.

If you would like to read the entire report on the respective output, you can download it by clicking on the

[Click here to download the full report of this intellectual output](#)

button.

Figure 15 Screenshot of the Intellectual Outputs Overview page

Below each intellectual output is an overview of all outputs (Figure 7), so that you can navigate directly to the individual outputs.

Learn more about the rest of intellectual outputs

Figure 16 Guide to the individual Intellectual Outputs

If you would like to read more about the IO#9, please click the button below to download the full report(Lemling & Masarykova, 2023).

[Please click here for the full report of this intellectual output](#)

EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

Aim of the intellectual output

An exploitation and sustainability plan to strengthen and foster both the dissemination of the project results and future cooperation among project partners, as well as with and among project-external HEI active in primary PETE, has been developed in the form of a document available online.

The output will contain guidance and service for the elaboration and implementation of respective cooperation agreements, with a special focus on the developed PETE course modules and micro-modules, made available also for project-external stakeholders.

Here you can find our ideas in to keep the PRIME PETE project active over the project duration:

Table 6 Goals and Tasks of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

Goal	Tasks
(1) Website update and maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refinement of reports for each IO • Refinement of modules template and related materials • Upload of the material • Maintenance of the website for the next 10 years
(2) Publication of results on university websites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University websites • EUPEA websites • AIESEP websites
(3) Communication through university newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University newsletters • EUPEA newsletter • AIESEP newsletter
(4) Presentation of results at national and international conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LTTs • MEs • EUPEA PE talk and AIESEP coffee connect • Identify relevant national and international conferences in the future
(5) Involvement and communication to relevant national and international associations and organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National associations (SISMeS, CAPDI, Consejo COLEF, IPPEA, ...) • International organizations (European Commission, UNESCO, OECD, WHO)
(6) Dissemination to the general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, ...) • Publication of the Handbook on ResearchGate & Erasmus+ platform • Publication on ZENODO

(7) Inclusion of modules and micromodules in PE university courses and CPD	• Inclusion of M and MM in university courses
	• Inclusion in CPD trainings proposed by relevant national associations
(8) Use of results to inform similar projects	• Inform projects such as EDUPASS, QualiTePE, ...
	• Apply for further projects

To read the complete exploitation and sustainability plan, please visit the [PRIME PETE Website](#).

If you would like to read more about the IO#10, please click the button below to download the full report (Carraro et al., 2023).

Please click here for the full report of this
intellectual output

The self-check tool and feedback report

One of the important outcomes of the project was the formulation of the dimensions and sub-dimensions, which helped to develop the modules and micro-modules. These dimensions and sub-dimensions could serve as a basis for a self-check process in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to evaluate the quality of the PETE programmes provided by the HEIs and also could be a motivation for extending the current PETE programmes.

The dimensions and sub-dimensions for self-evaluation are listed below in table 3. The white colour presents the core knowledge, skills, and competencies, the red colour presents the extended knowledge, skills, and competencies.

Go through the following **checklist** and consider whether the dimensions mentioned are part of the PE teacher education at your institution and mark either the **yes** or **no** column.

The dimensions marked no represent **gaps** in the education programme.

Visit the **PRIME PETE website** with the [overview of the teaching modules](#) and identify in the table which **modules cover the gaps** you have identified.

Visit the pages at the **PRIME PETE website** where the corresponding modules and micro-modules are presented and look at the contents. Download the summary **pdf document** and, if desired, the **teaching materials**.

Adapt the modules to your target group - have fun with them!

Table 7 Self-check tool for modules and micro modules based on the dimensions and sub-dimensions

Dimension 1: KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND MANAGEMENT	Dimensions' Code	Yes	No
Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills	D1K1		
Knowledge about children's overall development	D1K2		
Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people	D1K3		
Knowledge and understanding of the cultures of physical activity, physical education, and sport	D1K4		
Ability to use basic educational research, and applying existing theories and educational methods, to enhance teaching	D1S1		
Ability to arrange pedagogical work in line with policies of an education system and educational theories	D1S2		
Ability to use evidence-based educational theories and practices and ignore pseudoscientific claims and programmes	D1S3		
Capacity and autonomy to modify and adapt core educational and curricular policies to pedagogical practice	D1C1		
Advanced knowledge and understanding of holistic and learner-focused educational approaches to physical education and health education	D1K5		
Advanced knowledge and understanding of the role and significance of the body as a means of creative expression and artistic communication through exploration of a wide range of content within physical education	D1K6		
Advanced knowledge and critical understanding of sociological, philosophical, psychological and pedagogical theories in education and physical education	D1K7		
Capacity and responsibility to integrate key competency development to the physical education programme	D1C2		
Capacity and commitment to using physical education specific concepts and terminology appropriately	D1C3		
Capacity and commitment to critically reflect on educational policies	D1C4		

Dimension 2: TEACHING, LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT	Dimensions' Code	Yes	No
Advanced knowledge and understanding for cross-thematic and interdisciplinary teaching in physical education	D2K1		
Ability to plan and teach quality physical education lessons	D2S1		
Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment	D2S2		
Ability to plan long-term and short-term physical education programmes based on students' developmental level and readiness	D2S3		
Ability to demonstrate correctly, or provide a correct demonstration through a third party, of all major skills and tactics central to the relevant curriculum	D2S4		
Ability to using digital technology for learning and assessment	D2S5		
Advanced knowledge of group dynamics (including conflict management) and student-centred strategies	D2K2		
Advanced knowledge of the national curriculum	D2K3		
Advanced knowledge and understanding of different motor learning theories, and typical and atypical motor development, and practical consequences	D2K4		
Advanced knowledge on how to measure, reflect and evaluate physical education programmes	D2K5		
Ability to promote efficient use of movement time	D2S6		
Ability to use observation, self- and peer-assessment in physical education lessons and programmes	D2S7		
Ability to use teaching skills to support learning in different learning environments	D2S8		
Capacity and commitment to cooperate with other teachers and develop school curricula based on reflection	D2C1		
Capacity and commitment to cooperate with other teachers and develop school curricula based on reflection	D2C2		
Capacity and commitment to using different teaching strategies and model-based teaching in physical education lessons	D2C3		
Analyze and critique playgrounds, outdoor areas and parks as places for learning in physical education	D2K1		

Dimension 3: LEARNER EMPOWERMENT, POTENTIAL, DIVERSITY AND CREATIVITY	Dimensions' Code	Yes	No
Advanced knowledge of inclusion principles and practices	D3K1		
Ability to support learners in identifying own strengths and setting goals to build on these	D3S1		
Ability to work together with special education professionals, and adapt learning tasks to the individual needs of the students	D3S2		
Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels	D3C1		
Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment	D3C2		
Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence	D3C3		
Advanced knowledge and commitment to the application of the concept of the student as an active learner, thinker, mover and problem solver engaging with the content of the physical education curriculum	D3K2		
Advanced knowledge and understanding to recognize and differentiate healthy competitive and non-competitive concepts	D3K3		
Advanced knowledge of school counselling processes and of how to advise students (and their families/guardians) to develop learners' resources	D3K4		
Ability to build upon students' previous experiences, active participation, and creativity	D3S3		
Ability to design autonomy supported learning environment, and mastery learning	D3S4		
Ability to motivate students to practice sport activities in collaboration with peers, families and sport coaches	D3S5		
Ability to support students learning through an examination of a range of resources and equipment related to teaching physical education	D3S6		

Dimension 4: VALUES, SOCIAL LEADERSHIP AND COMMUNICATION	Dimensions' Code	Yes	No
Advanced knowledge and understanding as to how physical activity can be promoted in the whole-school context	D4K1		
Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and nonverbally	D4S1		
Ability to promote ethical behavior in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting	D4S2		
Ability to reflect on personal capacity, qualities and competencies as a subject leader in physical education	D4S3		
Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students	D4C1		
Capacity and commitment to respect different values, when interacting with people in contexts of diversity (social, ethnic, economic, political) and learn from that diversity	D4C2		
Capacity and commitment to adhere to children's rights	D4C3		
Advanced knowledge of ethical and professional standards, including knowledge about the constitution of appropriate relationships with learners	D4K2		
Ability to create situations for recognizing and understanding fair-play	D4S4		
Ability to organize extracurricular activities, and other educational events in response to social need	D4S5		
Capacity and commitment to take responsibility to promote and/or initiate teamwork among learners	D4C4		
Capacity and commitment to work with external providers to support learning in physical education	D4C5		
Capacity and commitment to promoting responsible and critical use of social media and communication technologies among learners	D4C6		

Dimension 5: DEVELOPMENT AS REFLECTIVE PROFESSIONALS AND LIFE-LONG LEARNERS	Dimensions' Code	Yes	No
Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for physical education in the school and beyond	D4K1		
Capacity and commitment to make use of colleagues, professional organizations and resources to develop as a reflective practitioner	D4S1		
Capacity and commitment to “cultural literacy” to support students coming from other cultures	D4S2		
Advanced knowledge of main sources of information that permit teachers to stay updated with general and physical education-related educational research and developments	D4S3		
Ability to critically examine educational research and developments (publications, events, resources, etc.) in search of solutions for challenges experienced in own classroom	D4C1		
Ability to develop adequate coping strategies, social support or preventive identification and influencing of stressors in the private and professional context	D4C2		
Ability to promote health and wellbeing concept by supporting active reflection about their job	D4C3		
Capacity and commitment to critically reflect and work on consistency of own personal and professional identity	D4K2		
Capacity and commitment to identify opportunities for collaboration and professional dialogue where teachers can develop networks, undertake peer observations and engage in collaborative professional learning	D4S4		
Capacity and commitment to ongoing professional development through the design of a professional development plan to guide growth as a physical education teacher	D4S5		

Conclusion

This handbook and guidance material IO#8 is designed to support the easy and flexible implementation of the modular PRIME PETE programme. The PRIME PETE programme is innovative as it is the first online European programme for primary teachers available with a focus on PE. With the help of the handbook and guidance material, the readers receive an overview of the project in general as well as an insight into Intellectual Outputs implemented. Subsequently, guidance material has been developed to support the implementation of the PRIME PETE programme to adapt to one's own context.

The PRIME PETE programme is characterized by a collaborative process between the project partners and teacher educators as well as the inclusion of students during the Learning Teaching and Training events and Professional Development events. The project partners hope that the website and its resources will make a significant contribution to supporting the work of teacher educators in providing enhanced quality primary PE. The PRIME PETE programme allows the interested HEI and teacher education institutions who are currently offering primary PETE programmes or those who are developing programmes to choose appropriate modules and micro-modules for flexible use and implementation. All the outputs from the project, as well as other materials created to meet the requirements of the training and professional development events, have been included in the website (<https://www.primepete.com>).

Due to the availability of PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules that are ready for implementation by stakeholders, expected impact and transferability potential includes sharing of the modules to facilitate engagement in student and teacher mobility, as one major objective beyond the project lifetime.

The PRIME PETE partners wish you pleasure in exploring our programme and success in their own adaptations and implementation. If you have any questions or comments, the partners will be happy to share their expertise and welcome your suggestions.

References

- Adamakis, M., & Scheuer, C. (2023). *Evaluation study and report* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #7].
- Adamakis, M., Scheuer, C., Carraro, A., & Santi, G. (2023). Method and tool to evaluate the PETE course modules and micro-modules [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #6].
- Carraro, A., Santi, G., Ries, F., Adamakis, M., & Lemling, A. (2023). *Exploitation and Sustainability Plan* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #10].
- González Ferreras, J. M. & Yarosh, M. (Eds.) (2018). *CALOHEE –Tuning Guidelines and Reference Points for the Design and Delivery of Degree Programmes in Teacher Education*. Groningen: University of Groningen.
- Lemling, A., & Masarykova, D. (2023). *Open course platform* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #9].
- Marron, S., Murphy, F., Onofre, M., Martins, J., Ferro, N., Rodrigues, A., Carraro, A., Santi, G., Scheuer, C., & Lemling, A. (2023). *Modular Primary PETE programme consisting of course modules and micro-modules* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #5].
- Masarykova, D., Scheuer, C., Lemling, A., Adamakis, M., Heck, S., Bailey, R., Onofre, M., Martins, J., Ferro, N., Rodrigues, A., Carraro, A., Tortella, P., & Csányi, T. (2023). *Overview on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education in Europe* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #1].
- Macphail, A., Tannehill, Y. & Avşar, Z. (2019). *European Physical Education Teacher Education practices*. Meidenhead: Meyer & Meyer Sport. ISBN: 978-1-78255-177-5
- Onofre, M., Ferro, N., Martins, J., Rodrigues, A., Carraro, A., Scheuer, C., Bailey, R., Adamakis, M., Heck, S., & Lemling, A. (2023). *Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #2].
- Repond, R.-M., Csányi, T., Scheuer, C., Ries, F., Carraro, A., Onofre, M., Martins, J., Ferro, N., & Rodrigues, A. (2023). *Primary Physical Education Teacher Profile* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #3].
- Ries, F., Carraro, A., Santi, G., & Scheuer, C. (2023). *Theoretical and Methodological Framework for Primary Physical Education Teacher Education in Europe* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #4].